

VELOCITY ACCOMMODATION DURING GFRP/METAL FRETTING CONTACTS

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ABSTRACT

The increase in industrial applications of glass fibre reinforced polymers requires new developments for a better compatibility with metallic parts. In the case of unstuck assemblies, small displacement vibrational contact can induce specific damaging processes. Fretting tests have been performed with E glass/epoxy unidirectional composite/aluminium alloy counterfaces. Results were collected by means of friction logs and Running Condition Fretting Maps. The degradations were analysed using Material Response Fretting Maps. The effect of fibre orientations was studied. All of these results were used to discuss the wear behaviour of GFRP/metal vibrating contacts through the new concept of Velocity Accommodation Mechanisms.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is now well known that fretting can appear to be a limiting factor in the development of new materials or coatings. This difficulty is increased due to the fact that wear properties are not intrinsic for a given material and that we have to consider the pairing in the case of non homogeneous contacts.

This fretting behaviour should now be considered in the case of fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) which are increasingly being used. Automotive or aeronautical applications of high performance FRP require assemblies with metallic components and thus an improvement in the knowledge of metal/FRP contacts.

Fibre nature and orientations versus fretting resistance have been described as main parameters, and hybrid materials have been proposed to optimize wear resistance (1 - 4). Of course, these results depend on the nature of the counterface and its roughness appears as a major parameter (3).

Contact conditions were shown to be mainly related to the normal loading, to the displacement amplitude, to the displacement rate and finally to the relative humidity and temperature levels (3, 5, 6).

Recently, wear has been analysed through interface tribology concepts which attempt to describe wear strength from third body behaviour (7) and velocity accommodation mechanisms (8, 9). Furthermore wear maps have been introduced to give accurate analysis of contact conditions and to determine the associated material responses (10). These last three approaches have been used to study metal-composite behaviour under fretting conditions.

2. TEST CONDITIONS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Test conditions

Fretting tests were conducted using a device already described elsewhere (10). The principle is given in Figure 1.

Experimental conditions :

- Imposed displacement, D
 $\pm 10 \mu\text{m} \rightarrow \pm 100 \mu\text{m}$
- Normal load, L
 $100 \rightarrow 2000 \text{ N}$
- Frequency, f
 $0.1 \rightarrow 25 \text{ Hz}$
- Number of cycles, N
 $1 \text{ up to } 2.10^6$

Figure 1. Fretting device.

Tests were performed in a conditioned room ($22^\circ \text{C} \pm 2$ and $\text{RH} = 50 \%$). All the results discussed in this paper were obtained under a frequency of 5 Hertz. Triangular shape displacement was applied under the initially imposed normal loading. For each cycle the tangential load F required to impose the displacement was continuously recorded as a function of the displacement D to obtain tangential force displacement cycles.

2.2 Materials

The FRP was an unidirectional E glass fibre-epoxy resin material obtained by filament winding (50 % volumic fibre content). Main mechanical properties determined under flexural testing are : $E = 34 \text{ GPa}$; $\sigma_f = 1200 \text{ MPa}$; $\epsilon_f = 3.7 \%$. GFRP parallelepipedic specimens ($10 \times 3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$) were cut in $350 \times 270 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ plates. The tested surface was polished up to a $1 \mu\text{m}$ diamond paste.

The metallic counterface was made of a 2024 aluminium alloy, thermomechanically treated T 351 : its ultimate tensile strength was 475 MPa and its fatigue limit ($R = .1$ under tensile testing) was 180 MPa with a fracture toughness K_{IC} of $33 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. The metallic specimens were alumina polished $10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ cubes, with a roughness $R_a : 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. In order to locate the contact area, the metallic specimens were slightly curved with a mean 1 meter radius.

Three orientations have been considered - Figure 2 - :

Figure 2. Fibre orientation as compared to the contacting surface.

For each case, the contact surface was $3 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ which induced a smaller real contact area due to the curvature ($R = 1 \text{ m}$) of the aluminium alloy counterface. The fixed specimen was the GFRP.

3. FRICTION LOGS AND RUNNING CONDITIONS FRETTING MAPS

Tangential force - displacement cycles were plotted versus the number of cycles in a three dimensional "tangential force - displacement - logarithm of number of cycles" curve called a "friction log". Examples of friction logs associated with the three main fretting regimes are given in Figure 3. We can observe :

- i) a closed cycle corresponding to a linear increase in the tangential load with the increase of displacement, the accommodation occurs due to the elasticity of both the fretting frame and the fretting contact. This is called the stick regime.
- ii) quasi-perpendicular cycles with initial increases in the maximum tangential load are related as the gross slip regime.
- iii) changes in the cycle shape with predominance of elliptic cycles are characteristic of a more complicated regime called the mixed regime. Very often an elliptic cycle is representative of sticking in the centre of the contact zone and sliding around this zone.

Test conditions :

$L = 200 \text{ N}, D = \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$

Test conditions :

$L = 400 \text{ N}, D = \pm 50 \mu\text{m}$

Test conditions :

$L = 200 \text{ N}, D = \pm 50 \mu\text{m}$

Figure 3. Friction logs corresponding to the main fretting regimes in the case of AP specimens.

The analysis of F-D cycles from testing of about 20 "normal load - displacement amplitude" pairings enabled us to plot the Running Condition Fretting Maps (RCFM) - Figure 4.-. In fixed experimental conditions, that is normal loading L and displacement D, these maps give the kind of friction logs obtained. For the three orientations, we noted mainly an increase in the stick regime due to the decreasing stiffness of the FRP sample from the P to the N orientation:

Figure 4. Running Conditions Fretting Maps for the three orientations.

The main differences in the location of the fretting regimes resulted from the changes of the contact stiffness due to the anisotropic properties of the UD composites material.

Results giving the qualitative evolution of wear have been presented for the three orientations using the material response fretting maps. However, such comparison requires a good knowledge of the contact conditions. Here the previous running condition fretting maps are difficult to analyse as the stiffness of the specimens depends on their orientation. This induces far different values of the contact stiffnesses due to the large anisotropy of the composite modulus. Indeed, the slopes of the F-D curves varied with the fibre orientations for the same applied conditions. Thus the real displacement between the two contacting surfaces depends on the surface nature but also on the orientation itself. One must be very careful when comparing the response of the specimens as the real displacement can be far different (examples are given in Table 1).

Table 1. Real displacement between the two contacting surfaces after 100 fretting cycles.

Imposed displacement (mm) (L = 200 N)	real displacement (mm)		
	P	AP	N
35	30	18	5
50	45	22	10

Fretting maps have been plotted considering the real displacement instead of the imposed displacement. Of course, the main drawback of these diagrams is the closing of the sticking domain for which the real displacement is nearly equal to zero. A comparison of two RCFMs are given in Figure 5 for N orientation :

Figure 5. Running condition fretting maps plotted for the real displacement (D_r) in the case of N specimens, as compared with maps plotted with the imposed displacement (D_i) ($N = 100$).

In this case, the real displacement remained very low compared to the imposed displacement as a consequence of both the composite stiffness and the indentation of the fibres at the contact edge. In

fact, the real displacement has often been shown to be the main factor controlling the particle detachment processes.

4. MATERIALS DAMAGING AND MATERIAL RESPONSE FRETTING MAPS

The main damage description is complex in the case of the FRP materials. Indeed, whatever the fretting conditions, fibre breaking and matrix microcracking were noted. Furthermore macrocrack initiation at the contact edge was only related to the N orientation. Four "material response" domains were defined with increasing displacement D from the FRP surface and cross section examinations :

- i) small grooves on the surface. This damage remained located at the contact limits and reached a maximum value of less than $5\ \mu\text{m}$ in depth. This feature was called non degradation (ND).
- ii) simultaneously :
 - breaking of glass fibres which could separate from the matrix and form glass fragments. These debris moved on the surface and could remain in their own area .
 - more or less intensive microcracking of the matrix; this cracking phenomenon did not induce matrix platelets to detach at first. This is probably due to the too low real displacement of the two contacting surfaces.

In order to distinguish this response from large crack initiation and propagation, this domain was called fibre and matrix breaking (FMB) - Figure 5 and Figure 6 -.

- iii) breaking of glass fibres and microcracking of the matrix could induce the formation of a powder bed with an increasing displacement amplitude. This powder bed was shown to contain glass particles, matrix powder and small platelets and also aluminium oxides. By analogy to previous work on homogeneous contacts, this domain was called the "particle detachment" (PD) domain (P and AP orientation) - Figure 6 -.
- iv) A macroscopic cracking could develop at the contact edges, following fibre-matrix interfaces. This delamination-like feature was related to a cracking (C) domain - Figure 7 - (N orientation).

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of the worn surface of the composite : microcracking of the matrix (P orientation) (L = 200N; D = $\pm 25\ \mu\text{m}$; N = 50000 cycles)

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of the worn surface of the composite : breaking of glass fibres (AP orientation) and bed of matrix, glass and metallic particles (L = 200N; D = $\pm 50\ \mu\text{m}$; N = 50000 cycles)

Figure 7. Optical micrograph in the case of the N orientation showing a macroscopic crack at the contact edge ($L = 200N$; $D = \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$; $N = 50000$ cycles).

Three Material Response Fretting Maps (MRFMs) were plotted at 5×10^4 cycles corresponding to the three orientations - Figure 8 -. MRFMs give an overview of the degradation mechanism at a given number of cycles.

Figure 8. Material Response Fretting Maps at 5×10^4 cycles. ND = Non Degradation, FMB = Fibre and Matrix Breaking, PD = Particle Detachment, C = Cracking. We note that the cracking domain only appeared for the N specimens.

As for many pairings (homogeneous or not), the gross slip domain of the RCFM corresponds, at first approximation, to the particle detachment domain of the MRFM.

The analyses of the aluminium alloy surfaces indicated the following damage :

- i) particle detachment : the metallic debris mixed with the resin and fibre debris. This feature was characteristic of the high displacement amplitude : the formation and the trapping of the debris bed prevented further damage of the metal.
- ii) Indentation of the glass fibres was noted in the case of N fibres.
- iii) Grooves were observed for P or AP fibre orientation. The thickness of these grooves was about $17 \mu\text{m}$, that is the diameter of the glass fibre for P specimens. Small cracks were noted in the grooves for the low displacement values.

Trapping of the debris was shown to be more difficult in the case of P fibre orientation. Cross sections indicated that the thickness of the metallic damaged layers remained very small ($< 20 \mu\text{m}$) for all the tested conditions. This proves the protective effect of the powder beds.

5. VELOCITY ACCOMMODATION MECHANISMS (V.A.M.)

Recently Y. Berthier and al (8, 9) have shown that the analysis of wear requires the localisation of the site in which the difference in velocity between the two rubbing surfaces (first bodies) is accommodated. Furthermore, four modes of accommodation, labelled M_1 to M_4 have been identified : they correspond to the elastic, rupture, shear or rolling modes. They were noted in the first bodies, in the layer separating the rubbing surfaces and in the interfacial screens (nanometer thick layers) on the first body. These twenty mechanisms govern both friction and wear. In the case of fibre reinforced polymers, this general approach requires the taking into account of viscoelasticity which can add dissipative modes of accommodation. The initial accommodation process induces the initial contact regime and thus the strain and stress fields suffered by the first bodies (composite material and aluminium alloys). In the case of homogeneous contact, the same kind of alloys were shown to damage by cracking under the stick and mixed regime or by particle detachment from work hardened superficial layers under the gross slip regime (10). Obviously, the stick and mixed regimes appear to be the most detrimental for a durability point of view.

In our experiments, GFRP suffered the first damages whatever the fretting regime. Very often, the first strokes induced a modification in the nature of the contact (stick, partial slip, gross slip) and favour the stick regime -Figure 9-.

Figure 9. Modification of the cycle shapes along the test in the case of the AP and N orientations.

In the case of the N orientation, the sticking was related to the indentation of the glass fibres in the aluminium surface. Then the velocity was entirely accommodated in the composite material. The maximum stresses located at the contact limits initiated cracks and the main velocity accommodation mechanism soon became the opening of coarse cracks which developed up to several millimetres in depth. On the other hand, the aluminium counterface was no longer strained and no damage was

detected : the velocity accommodation by cracking of the first body with the lowest shearing resistance prevents any damage of the counterface.

In the case of the A or AP orientations, the increase in sticking appeared as a consequence of the polymeric layer separating the surface and no crack was observed in the composite or in the aluminium alloy.

For the three orientations, the VAMs induced by the composite material constitutive elements prevented any degradation of the metallic counterface which was severely damaged when contacting aluminium alloys under the same fretting loadings.

Under the slip regimes the velocity was accommodated in the thick powder bed formed by polymeric, glass and oxide debris which prevented any further damage as the debris bed was strongly trapped in the contact.

6. CONCLUSION

The fretting behaviour of heterogeneous contacts was explained using two sets of fretting maps and the concept of velocity accommodation mechanism. The local loading, the material damaging and the accommodation mechanisms interact all along the test. Therefore any comparison of materials requires a strong interaction between mechanical and material approaches. Furthermore, in the case of anisotropic materials, the same external loading induces far different local loading because of the differences in the material stiffnesses (RCFMs).

We must avoid analysing differences in fretting behaviour through material properties if we have not made sure that the local loadings are similar. The development of this fretting wear approach using two sets of maps and the concept of velocity accommodation mechanisms appear to be very powerful in controlling the fretting fatigue behaviour of composite materials.

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DELAMINATION

